

1. Relationship between Smoking and Endodontic Variables in Hypertensive Patients. 2011.

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The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between smoking and the prevalence of apical periodontitis and root canal treatment in hypertensive patients. In a cross-sectional study, the records of 100 hypertensive patients, 50 smokers and 50 nonsmokers, were examined. Periapical status of all teeth was assessed by using the periapical index score. Apical periodontitis in 1 or more teeth was found in 92% of smoker patients and in 44% of nonsmoker subjects ($P=.000$; odds ratio [OR], 16.8; 95% confidence interval [CI], 4.6-61.3). One or more root-filled teeth were found in 58% and 20% of smoker and nonsmoker subjects, respectively ($P < .01$; OR, 5.5; 95% CI, 2.3-13.5). Among smoker hypertensive patients, 6% of the teeth had apical periodontitis, whereas in the nonsmoker subjects, 2% of teeth were affected ($P < .01$; OR, 3.3; 95% CI, 2.0-5.4). The percentage of root-filled teeth in the smoker and nonsmoker groups was 3.6% and 1.2%, respectively ($P < .01$; OR, 2.9; 95% CI, 1.6-5.5). The prevalence of apical periodontitis and root canal treatment was significantly higher in smoker hypertensive patients compared with nonsmoker subjects.

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